

TEACHING SPEAKING SKILL BY THE METHOD OF PICTURE BASED STORIES

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Annotatsiya. Bu akademik tadqiqot, gaplashish ko'nikmalarini o'qitish jarayonida hikoya qilishning roli va ahamiyatiga e'tibor qaratgan. Tadqiqot, talabalarning gapirish malakalarini rivojlantirishda hikoya qilish va uni qayta aytish texnikalarini qo'llashning ahamiyatini zarur ekanligini bildiradi. Asosiy maqsad, qayta aytish uslubini o'qitishning talabalarning gapirish qobiliyatlari rivojlanishiga va samarali bo'lishiga ta'sirini tushuntirish. Kirish qismi tadqiqotning asosiy mavzusini, metodologiyasini va muhim topishmalarini ta'riflaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: nutq qobiliyatlari, hikoyalarni takrorlash, hikoya qilish texnikasi, takrorlash usuli, rivojlanish, samaradorlik

Аннотация. Главная цель начального обучения иностранному языку заключается в развитии устной беглости. В процессе изучения иностранного языка общение обычно включает в себя воспроизведение и имитацию, с активностями, направленными на создание точного выхода с близкой поддержкой. Однако для достижения беглости и основных навыков устной речи требуется не только механическое воспроизведение запомненных языковых единиц. В сущности, для продвижения в освоении целевого языка и достижения подлинной коммуникативной компетенции учащиеся также должны продемонстрировать способность использовать язык спонтанно и креативно. В данной статье предлагается подход для улучшения дискурсивных навыков в развитии устной коммуникации.

Ключевые слова: речевые навыки, пересказ рассказов, техника рассказывания, метод пересказа, развитие, результативность.

Abstract. This academic research focuses on the role and significance of retelling stories in the process of teaching speaking skills. The study recognizes the importance of incorporating storytelling and retelling techniques in enhancing students' speaking proficiency. The primary objective is to investigate the facilitative impact of teaching the retelling approach on the development and effectiveness of students' speaking abilities. The introduction provides an overview of the main theme, methodology, and key findings of this research.

Keywords: speaking skills, retelling stories, storytelling techniques, retelling approach, development, effectiveness

INTRODUCTION. The main aim of learning English in most parts of the world is to be able to use it for communication. Language is not a set of rules, meaning that teaching English is done to prepare students to use English in daily life, e.g. to have communicative competence. The aim of teaching speaking is to train the students to be able to have meaningful and contextual communicative skills in real life situations

The speaking activity required for oral communication is designed to activate the spoken communication, students are expected to actually do things with language and it is the “doing”

that should be the main focus of such sessions. Unfortunately, in reality it is that the students in school today are still reluctant to perform oral communication in English [Burnkart, 1998]

A language lesson consists of a sequence of activities that lead to the lesson goals or objectives. A lesson is normally devoted to more than one type of activity and the teacher often has a “script” or preferred sequence that she follows when teaching a particular lesson. Ideally, the sequence of activities will leave the students feeling that they have successfully achieved the goal for the lesson [Richards & Bohlke, 2011, p. 3]. Because of that, the teacher should strive to provide an appropriate and stimulating teaching-learning experience with a context and situation which will lead to student success.

Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) can help the students to develop an appropriate English context [Richards, 2006]. This methodology is learner-centered with emphasis on communications in real-life situations. In CLT, students can practice everyday situations in real daily life.

To gain success in teaching speaking skills, we decided to try the use of Picture Strip Stories in CLT as one of the methods to boost students’ speaking skills in class. Activities in CLT typically involve students in real or realistic communications, where the successful achievement of the communicative task that they are performing is at least as important as the accuracy of their language use [Harmer, 2002, p. 69].

The Picture Strip Story technique relies heavily on visual aids to convey ideas. By working in groups, the students can negotiate meanings and verbalize to support their own ideas in role play. During the role play, the students perform, using their English speaking ability in relation to the material/visual aids as their task. The purposes of combining the different techniques are to get the students to inform, persuade and entertain with little verbal participation from the teacher. When using the Picture Strip Stories for CLT, the teacher plans and delivers an oral presentation in a manner that allows much participation from the students and helps direct them towards the desired learning outcomes [Richards, 2006, p. 20].

Research Questions

1. To what extent can the use of picture strip stories help students enhance their speaking abilities?
2. In what sub-skills of speaking will the students perform better after being taught by using picture strip stories?

Research Objectives

1. To find out whether using the picture strip story technique with CLT will significantly help students develop their speaking ability.
2. To find out what aspects of speaking the students will perform better if any, after being taught using picture strip stories as CLT.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Teaching Speaking and Definition of a Picture Strip Story

Speaking is a crucial part of second language learning and teaching. Despite its importance, for many years, many English language teachers have taught speaking just as a repetition of drills or memorization of dialogues [Brown, 2007]. However, today the goal of teaching speaking should be to improve students’ speaking skills. Only in that way can students learn to express themselves

and learn how to follow the social and cultural rules appropriate in each communicative circumstance [Harmer, 2002; Pachler & Field, 2001].

According to Freemans [2000, p. 129] many teaching-learning activities can be done with picture strip stories; one of them is by giving a small group a strip story. A student in the group will then show the first picture of the story to the other members of her group and ask them to predict what the second picture is like. This activity is an example of using a strip story to conduct a problem-solving task as a communicative technique. They can be structured so that students share information or work together to arrive at a solution. This gives students practice in negotiating meaning. In short, a picture strip story is a series of pictures that have a story sequence, that are designed to be read as a narrative or as a chronicle in sequence. Teachers can use picture strip stories as visual aids to help students improve their speaking skills. This aid is useful to help make students find it easy to talk about something.

Another example of picture strip story implementation is provided by Allen and Valetta [1977, p. 240], who use picture strip story activity with short stories or anecdotes which have exactly the same number of sentences as there are students in the class or group. The sentences are individually written on separate strips of paper. If the same story is utilized across multiple classes, the sentences can be digitally typed, printed, photocopied, and subsequently cut into strips. Each student in the class or group receives a strip randomly, memorizing the sentence provided. Subsequently, the strips are gathered. Students, communicating solely in the target language, move around and inquire among themselves until they collectively reconstruct the entire original story. The teacher's role is primarily that of a facilitator, and it is advised that the teacher maintains silence during the reconstruction activity.

From the definitions above, concluded that speaking an attempt to teach something in the form of a story with sequential sentences or pictures that have been found to be effective in teaching speaking to students.

The Advantages and Disadvantages of Using Picture Strip Stories

According to Vernon, Gerlach and Donald [1980, p. 277] “using picture strip stories in teaching has advantages and disadvantages”. Some advantages of using picture strip stories in teaching-learning processes are:

- They are inexpensive and widely available.
- They provide common experiences for an entire group.
- The visual details make it possible to study the subject clearly.
- They offer a stimulus to further study because research shows that visual evidence is a powerful tool.
- They help to focus attention and to develop critical judgment.
- They are easily manipulated.

Besides these advantages, some disadvantages of picture strip stories when used in teaching and learning speaking are set out below [Vernon, Gerlach & Donald, 1980, p. 277]:

- Students pay more attention to the picture than to the material to be learned.
- It takes time and money to provide attractive pictures.
- Small, unclear pictures may cause problems in the teaching-learning process since the students may misunderstand the pictures.

- The classroom can become noisy when the students all work in groups at once.

To address these challenges, it is crucial to gain a thorough understanding of the specific techniques employed by teachers in their respective local contexts, along with the strategies implemented when facing difficulties or challenges in the application of these techniques. Teachers should adeptly handle their classrooms to establish an optimal learning atmosphere. This involves activities such as rearranging seating arrangements, boosting student confidence, capturing and sustaining students' attention and active participation, and occasionally resorting to the use of the first language (L1) if students encounter significant difficulty comprehending tasks in the target language (L2).

In conclusion, the Picture Strip Story technique is an effective technique to use for teaching speaking. The use of the Picture Strip Story in the teaching-learning process is stimulating and productive. The students became attentive and involved actively in the learning processes. Both the teacher and the students had active interactions during the teaching-learning processes by using the Picture Strip Story. The technique helped students to be bolder in speaking up and expressing their ideas so that they became more confident, creative, and motivated in learning and practicing speaking. Therefore, their speaking skills improved a lot.

This research confirmed that Picture Strip Story is one of the Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) techniques strongest tools that can be applied for teaching-learning speaking. The technique can help the students increase and empower their speaking ability in real communications. The Picture Strip Story is an effective technique for teaching-learning speaking.

Besides, the students who were taught by using Picture Strip Story had better performance in their speaking sub-skills, pronunciation, grammar, vocabulary, fluency, and comprehensibility. So, it can be concluded that the five speaking sub skills were better taught by using the Picture Strip Story technique.

Story in group work and role-play combined in the teaching- learning speaking activities, so they became more active in participating in the speaking activities in the classroom.

REFERENCES

1. Allen, D., & Valletta, R. M. (1977). *Classroom Techniques: Foreign Languages and English as A Second Language*. New York: Harcourt.
2. Brown, J. D. (2000). What is construct validity? *JALT Testing and Evaluation SIG Newsletter*, 4(2), 7–10.
3. Burnkart, G. S. (1998). *Modules For The Professional Preparation Of Teaching Assistants In Foreign Language*. Washington DC: Center for Applied Linguistics. Retrieved November 2003. Available at <http://www.nclrc.org/essentials/speaking/goalsspeak.htm>.
4. Freemans, D. L. (2000). *Techniques and Principles in Language Teaching*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
5. Harmer, J. (2002). *The Practice of English Language Teaching (Fourth Edition)*, Harlow: Longman.
6. Richards, J. C., & Bohlke, D. (2011). *Creating Effective Language Lesson*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
7. Vernon, S. G., & Donald, P. E. (1980). *Teaching and Media a Systematic Approach*. New Jersey: Prentice Hall.